

Project Brand Book

Executive Summary

- The purpose of this brand book is to assist the Consortium in using the CareUp logo appropriately.
- It is also a useful aid when instructing typographers and others assigned with the production of branded items to design and create CareUp communication materials in an adequate manner.
- To maintain the integrity of the visual identity of the project it is important to apply all the elements of the present guide properly and consistently.

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Project Logo (primary version)

The logo of the CareUp acts as the project's first connection with the audiences, and it is considered the cornerstone of a coherent visual identity to trademark the partners' work in any electronic and/or print outputs. It consists of the project emblem and the project acronym:

The logo should be used mainly on a white (i.e., bright and simple) background in its primary version for maximum impact and clarity.

Project Logo (negative version)

In cases of coloured and/or patterned backgrounds, the negative version of the project logo should be used to maintain contrast levels, thus ensuring proper visibility:

The logo should be used mainly on a white (i.e., bright and simple) background in its primary version for maximum impact and clarity.

Instructions (1/2)

Clear space surrounding the project logo should remain free of competing texts, logos, images or any other visual element that could interfere with the logo. The indicative space should be set at approximately $\frac{1}{2}$ of the logo dimensions.

Instructions (2/2)

The display of the project logo should comply with the versions that are specified in this guide. The logo may not appear in any other colors and versions than the predefined.

The logo should not be altered in any shape or format or even combined with any other element such as other logos, words, graphics, photos, slogans or symbols.

Colour scheme

The CareUp colour scheme is the following:

- Primary Colour: #0C6980 [Cerulean]
 - Secondary Colour 1: #8ec8d4 [Non Photo blue]
 - Secondary Colour 2: #4CA0B0 [Moonstone]
 - Secondary Colour 3: #FAB6AB [Melon]
 - Extra Colour 1: #FADADD [Misty rose]
 - Extra Colour 2: #FCE4EC [Lavender blush]
 - Extra Colour 3: #EFEFEE [Anti-flash white]

Important note:

- **CMYK colors** are used in **printing materials**, while **RGB colors** are used on **web applications**.

Font Family

The project uses two specific fonts:

- Poppins (for headings and titles)
- Calibri (for normal text, subtitles and captions)

These two fonts must be opted for all communication materials, online and print , as well as in web and media applications wherever this is possible (i.e. at the project website), to retain consistency. Replacing the given fonts should be avoided.

Poppins (Regular)
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890!@#&%*

Poppins (Regular)
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890!@#&%*

Poppins (Regular)
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890!@#&%*

Calibri (Regular)
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890!@#&%*

Calibri (Regular)
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890!@#&%*

Calibri (Regular)
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890!@#&%*

Text formats and configurations

Text Format	Configurations				
	Font	Size	Style	Colour	Alignment
Heading 1	Poppins	24	Normal	#OC6980	Justified
Heading 2	Poppins	18	Normal	#OC6980	Justified
Heading 3	Poppins	14	Normal	#OC6980	Justified
Heading 4	Poppins	12	Italics	#OC6980	Justified
Normal Text	Calibri	12	Normal	#000000	Justified
Captions	Calibri	11	Italics	#OC6980	Center